

**Smartphone Adoption Difficulties for Older Adults in Chengdu on the Interface Perspective:
A Qualitative Analysis**

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Information and communication technology has developed rapidly in the past decades, inducing the invention of various personal terminal devices including personal computers, iPads, smart televisions, and most importantly, smartphones. Smartphones have become an inseparable part of most people's lives as they integrate popular features such as communication, web access, entertainment, shopping, and payment in one portable device. Smartphone penetration rates in China have increased from 57.2% in 2018 to 71.8% in 2022 and are projected to rise to 82.8 percent by 2027 (Statista, 2020). Not everyone, however, is involved in this burst of smartphone adoption in China. On the contrary, the older people became increasingly marginalized in this process. As young users continue to pursue new features and apps as well as minimalist designs, smartphone manufacturers and service providers shape smartphones in a way that they become more and more complex, and older adults become increasingly marginalized in the process.

The different degrees of technology acceptance displayed by different individuals are leading to a "digital divide" in the world; older adults, who generally have lower education levels and less technological knowledge suffer from the inability to use technology compared to their younger counterparts (Mubarak & Suomi, 2022). Smartphones stand out as a representative of emerging technology: more and more aspects of everyday life are integrated into smartphones. As the demographic structure in China shifts towards a larger proportion of the older population, it becomes imperative to study the difficulties older people are facing.

1.2 Inquiry

This study focuses on qualitatively gaining insights into the barriers and difficulties that hinder older individuals in Chengdu from adopting smartphones, on the smartphone interface perspective. Chengdu, unlike metropolises such as Beijing or Shanghai, is seldom studied in this field, which signals an urgent need to conduct in-depth research, as further discussed in the literature review. Generalization to a bigger population like all the older adults across Chengdu or China, however, is not intended because of the unavailability of probability sampling discussed in the methodology section. The “interface” perspective simply means the interaction between the user and the device. Anything on the smartphone that confuses older adults and slows down the interaction counts in this perspective; on the contrary, difficulties due to the impairments of older people themselves are not counted. Factors that make older adults unable to understand and use functions efficiently or prevent further usage of smartphones are all considered to hinder the smartphone use of older adults. Through semi-structured interviews followed by a thematic analysis of collected data, this study aims to identify and evaluate these factors in current smartphone design and achieve a deeper understanding of older people’s smartphone adoption barriers and concerns that can provide directions for future studies.

1.3 Hypothesis

The researcher hypothesizes that the main and most common cause of smartphone usage difficulties among older adults is the complex in-app navigation among various features. Smartphone apps today tend to integrate as many features as possible; a widely-used Chinese dictionary app, Youdao, for example, has recently added a video stream function on its homepage in an attempt to attract young users, which has no relation with its purpose as mobile dictionary

application. More and more apps in China are integrating popular features that might not enhance the user experience at all, characterized by the development of video streams in utility, communication, shopping, and virtually all other kinds of apps, making even the experienced users confused sometimes.

2. Literature Review

To understand how the inquiry of this study contributes new perspectives for the academic society, it is crucial to first look into how the existing scholarly works evaluate the problem. This section contextualizes the investigation of this study in the larger academic community, crediting the works that elicited this study while identifying gaps and justifying the importance of this study.

Searching keywords: Smartphones, Older adults, Difficulties, Barriers, Usability barriers.

Databases: Springer Link, ResearchGate, NIH, Google Scholar, CNKI.

2.1 Older Adults and Their Inability to Use Smartphones

A correlation between old age and the inability to use smartphones has been repeatedly identified in past technology adoption studies. A study conducted by Abdullah and Zain (2019) on urban and suburban older smartphone users aims to uncover issues of older adults using smartphones. In the study, older adults as well as more experienced young users were asked to perform the same sequence of tasks on smartphones. The researchers described a high error rate for older adults performing slightly more complex operations, such as adding new contact numbers and accessing internet applications. The researchers concluded that although older adults have the potential to handle more complex operations instead of only basic usage under proper

guidance, they still make more errors before someone teaches them (Abdullah & Zain, 2019). In another study, the researcher asked older adults to use the interface as instructed and recorded their actions as well as issues for activity analysis. The study concluded that older adults “were able to effectively navigate through content, such as lists, galleries, or cards,” but “with direct manipulation, even a very simple gesture can create significant difficulties for older adults due to their decreased motor capabilities.” (Li & Luximon, 2019) The study acknowledged decent usability for content-orientated design, but suggests that difficulties still have a heavy presence in smartphone navigation for older adults, especially in menu navigations.

2.2 Existing Analysis for the Cause of Usability Barriers

With the realization of usability barriers between older adults and smartphone technologies, the scholarly community has made efforts to analyze the cause of the problem. Researchers from different parts of the world have used various methods in an attempt to investigate the driving factors that made smartphones seemingly unfavorable or even unusable for older adults. A literature review conducted by Paez and Rio (2019) identified three major factors: visual limitations, psychomotor limitations, and cognitive limitations. Mohadis and Ali (2014) conducted a field study on Malaysian older adults consisting of interviews and statistical analysis, which identified “financial restrictions, vision impairment and lack of knowledge in using smartphone functionalities” to be the major barriers that prevent the elderly from using smartphones. Zhou’s (2013) study with elders in Beijing points to age-related differences in requirements for mobile phones, with older adults placing more emphasis on visible attributes and facing difficulties. Older adults “were not confident to use mobile phones,” and have more problems with soft keys and multi-tap than younger adults. Another interesting insight is the influence of learning methods on

smartphone adoption. Researchers found that elders preferred manuals to the trial-and-error method, and inadequate design of manuals can make it difficult for them to adopt smartphones. (Leung et al., 2012)

2.3 Filled Gaps

1) Regional specification: This study is a field study conducted in communities in Chengdu, China. Literature on this topic is mostly conducted out of China, in Malaysia, or the Americas (Mohadis & Ali, 2014; Paez & Rio, 2019; Leung et al., 2012). Studies conducted in China all focus on metropolises like Beijing, Tianjin, Shanghai, etc. (Zhou, 2013). This study is the first to assess the barriers to smartphone adoption for older adults in Chengdu, which has a unique demographic structure and technological implementation rates.

2) New perspective: This study focuses on the cause of the problem from a broad interface perspective. Existing literature evaluated mainly the perspective of the older adults themselves i.e. their financial limitations, physical impairments, and cognitive inabilities (Mohadis & Ali, 2014; Paez & Rio, 2019; Leung et al., 2012; Zhou, 2013). The design of smartphones themselves is a rather untouched perspective for field studies of similar purposes.

3) Timeliness: Smartphone technology develops at a rapid pace. This study reviews how older adults' gap with the most recent smartphone interface, while most existing studies are conducted before 2020, evaluating the problem in the context of outdated smartphone technology.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Aims

As stated in the introduction, the overarching topic of the research is qualitatively identifying the barriers and difficulties that hinder older individuals in Chengdu from adopting smartphones, from the smartphone interface perspective. To make the research aim more approachable, the topic is divided into two research questions:

- 1) What specific problems do older individuals usually experience with smartphone interfaces?
- 2) How can the interfacial problems that caused these experiences be classified into different themes?

Research question 1) serves as a preliminary step of data gathering, which is essential in allowing research question 2) to be answered. The findings related to research question 1) will be detailed in the appendices as interview transcripts. Question 2) will be directly answered and detailed in the results section.

Targeting these two problems, a set of methods including semi-structured interviews and thematic analysis is developed and discussed in the subsequent parts.

3.2 Participants

The data collection part of this study requires human participants to answer our interview questions. According to the Chinese Law of Protection of the Rights and Interests of Elderly

People (People's Republic of China, 2012), lawful Chinese citizens aged 60 and above are considered older adults. This study thus aims to find participants who:

- 1) Are aged 60 and above;
- 2) Currently reside in Chengdu;
- 3) Have used a smartphone for at least a year;
- 4) Have sufficient cognitive ability to convey his/her perceived issues to a researcher.

In practice, however, qualified participants are rather scarce in Chengdu. Finding a qualified participant takes up to 1-2 hours while the interview process itself usually goes on for no more than 10 minutes. Due to the unavailability of government residential databases, it is impractical to employ any form of random sampling, thus this study utilizes convenience sampling as the sampling strategy.

The participants are taken from very different districts/nursing homes in Chengdu to ensure coverage as good as possible (location and/or information detailed in appendix b):

1. Wuhou District [residents];
2. Xincheng Property Management [employees];
2. Lianghe District [residents];
3. Jinxin Jiujiulefu Nursing Home [residents].

3.3 Semi-Structured Interviews

This study employs a qualitative data collection method through semi-structured interviews. The semi-structured interview is a variant of the widely adopted interview method. Traditionally, interviews are conducted between two individuals, an interviewer and an interviewee, about a mutually interested topic. (Kvale, 1996) Generally, in interviews, a list of open-ended questions will be asked by the interviewer which is designed to obtain desired information from the interviewee (as cited by Sarib et al, 2022). From there, due to the method's significant applicability, many modified versions of interviews spawned as alternative qualitative approaches researchers can take. According to the results of Mashuri and Sarib, in terms of how "structured" the interviews are, they are classified as structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, and unstructured interviews. In structured interviews, researchers strictly follow a list of questions while unstructured interviews don't require a question list at all.

This study utilizes semi-structured interviews considering the study's goal and realistic constraints. Semi-structured interviews utilize a question list but don't require each question to be answered. Additional questions are also allowed. The interview part is designed to answer research question 1 (What specific problems do older individuals usually experience with smartphone interfaces?). This question requires the researcher to follow a topic throughout the interview (usability barriers of interface), and not to drift away to other aspects like social or ethical factors. During pilot tests with a few older people, however, it was found hard to expect an elder to respond to every question. Elders have different degrees of education and cognitive capabilities, thus there are frequent questions that an elder can hardly comprehend. In that case,

the researcher has to skip those questions or ask simple impromptu questions instead.

Alternatively, if an elder shows particular interest in a question, the researcher can ask further questions to get a better understanding of that topic. The proper number of interview participants is determined by the principle of saturation, which means that the process is completed when the main ideas and relevant ideas have been successfully identified, and new interviews barely generate any new content for the research (as cited by Weller et al., 2018).

The interview questions are formed under the guidebook developed by Roberts in 2020. The guide emphasizes that questions should be formed to elicit detailed and relevant responses, and also describes open-ended questions as particularly useful for exploring participants' experiences, perceptions, and feelings in depth, which is the goal of research question 1). The interview question list developed mainly contains open-ended questions that ask participants about specific difficult experiences they have encountered and are divided into sections including basic information, overall experiences, barriers and difficulties, assistance, etc. As mentioned before, interviewees are not expected to answer all of the questions; rather, they are expected to elaborate on those problems that they are interested in. All interviews were recorded or transcribed on the spot with permission. Ethical research guidelines were addressed by: 1) asking for verbal consent before each interview, informing the participants about the topic, approximate length of the interview, and permission for transcription; 2) keeping the interviews completely anonymous, without asking for any sensitive personal information. The full question list is available in Appendix 1, provided in both the original Chinese text and English translation.

3.4 Thematic Analysis

After data collection using semi-structured interviews, this study moves on to examining and analyzing the qualitative data using thematic analysis, which allows research question 2) to be answered. Thematic analysis is a method for “identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data” (Virginia & Victoria, 2006). It is a commonly used qualitative data analysis method for its remarkable flexibility and applicability. Much like other qualitative analysis method, thematic analysis can be either deductive or inductive. This study utilizes the inductive version, meaning that no pre-existing theoretical framework is adopted to situate the analysis, and thus allows broader and more expansive study (Michell & Lara, 2020). Inductive thematic analysis uncovers the underlying patterns behind collected data and then generates “themes” – a patterned response or meaning capturing something important in the data, as defined by Virginia and Victoria (2006). This study follows the guidelines developed by Michell and Lara (2020), utilizing a sixfold process: Familiarizing with data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and renaming themes, and producing the report.

A specific description of the whole thematic analysis process is presented here for the replicability of the method. Firstly, the recordings are transcribed into readable documents. The researcher first read the documents at least once. These documents are then repeatedly read while key sentences therein are highlighted to represent the different codes they generate. In this step, older adults’ experiences of encountering difficulties will be specially focused upon and clearly distinguished into corresponding codes. In the next step, instead of merely summarizing the codes, themes are generated by *interpreting* the codes of the data. For example, from a code of “faulty

interactions frequently happen on the menu page, leading to opening wrong apps,” the theme will emphasize on unclear design of the menu page, not “frequent error of menu page interaction” or other mere summary of the experiences. 4-5 themes are expected to appear in this step. Themes are then winnowed, reworded and adequately defined in a way that effectively conveys its idea, with no overlapping, leaving about 3-4 final themes. Since the participants are older residents in Chengdu, China, all steps until the report writing will be conducted in Chinese to yield the most original and accurate results. In report writing, all the themes and definitions will be translated into English, with extensive analysis as well as translated interview excerpts to illustrate each theme more vividly.

4. Results

Results from the comprehensive thematic analysis allow the smartphone using difficulties of older adults to be characterized by themes. This section will discuss the results of the thematic analysis, including recurring themes in the data and evidence from transcripts to provide necessary support and analysis. For reference, interview transcripts are provided in the Appendix. The definitions of themes that are discussed in the section are presented in Table 1 below:

THEMES	DEFINITIONS
Intrusive Advertising	Older adults experience difficulties related to the heavy presence of excess advertising on smartphones, some of which can be very intrusive and even dangerous, disrupting older adults’ smartphone experience. Related Codes: Advertisement Interrupting Interaction, Fear of False Purchases/Subscriptions.
Complexity	Older adults face increasingly complex interfaces as more functions are integrated into this small piece of hardware. Older adults have a hard time remembering how to use them. Related Codes: Complex Interaction, Too Many Buttons, Lack of Physical Buttons/Interactions.
Lack of Trust Cues	Older adults perceive a lack of trust cues for real and official information. As a result, older users are so concerned about online scams

that would rather not use new functions. Related Codes: Privacy Leaks, Online Scams, Fear of False Purchases/Subscriptions.

Table 1. Themes and Definitions

Notations used for the transcript excerpts are listed as follows:

[I] - Interviewer asking or interrupting

[...] - A portion skipped or omitted because of repetition or irrelevancy

(comments) - Added comments, typically explaining something in the transcript

4.1 Recurring Theme 1: Intrusive Advertising

The over-advertising problem has a heavy presence in interviews with older adults. Out of the 13 older adults interviewed, 7 mentioned the problem. Participants number 1, 4, 6, 7, 9, 12, and 13 complained about the advertisements infiltrating the smartphone interface, disturbing their user experience, sometimes leading to false purchases or subscriptions. Some participants complained very intensely about advertisements. Participant 12 said,

“I hate advertisements. [I] So annoying. I feel like there are more ads online than ever before.

There are so many places that ads can slip into, they are basically everywhere. Look at this message app, [...] they send me spam messages every day, all of them are ads. And this one says there’s another discount for paying my phone bill online now. [...] Some apps I use also send me things I don’t even want to read. [...] I’m a party member, and some older members use this messaging app instead of Wechat (A chatting app, similar to WhatsApp), because, you know, they can’t handle Wechat. Every day when I read the messages I had to click in these meaningless ads, I don’t know how to cancel them. And when I was watching videos, those ads also pop out. You

can do nothing about it. No, you can't close them sometimes."

Participant 6 reported the inability to distinguish ads from normal content, and that ads usually sneak in normal videos to make it less distinguishable for older adults.

"They (younger staff in the nursing home) told me not to click on the ads because they cheat money out of you. Sometimes I can't tell if those ads are part of the video, and they (young staff) sometimes blame me for watching ads all the time, because they don't know why I like ads that much. Actually, I just can't tell."

Participant 1, 4, and 5 all expressed that ads can feel very intrusive in their smartphone usage experience. Participant 4 stated that he changed his novel reading app because the previous one had too many ads. "It's like they have to show you a video, an ad, every few pages. That app seems completely free, but you are definitely going to lose money if you click on the ads."

Generally, the older adults described advertisements as annoying and intrusive, interrupting them from what they were doing. They also have a fear of online scams hiding in ads. In some cases, these intrusive ads even stop older adults from using certain apps. As the most frequently mentioned problem, intrusive advertising is one main difficulty that hinders older adults from using smartphones.

4.2 Recurring Theme 2: Complexity

From making calls and sending text messages to video gaming and live streaming, functions and corresponding operations in the smartphone interface have evolved to become more complex

than ever before. Simpler cell phones back then only took a few physical buttons to operate, yet smartphones now require users to perform a combination of operations in the navigation menu to use a function. Young users may adapt to the new features, yet older adults have a harder time using them. Participants 1, 2, 5, 8, and 13 all mentioned that they are overwhelmed by the complexity of modern smartphones.

“Maybe it’s the young people, they are in charge now, and so they made everything more complex. I bet they don’t have a problem using it,” said Participant 2, “but I sometimes lose track of the operations on the phone. You know, I have a bad memory now, I can’t remember what I want to do when I enter some pages. There were buttons everywhere, I don’t think I even need those functions, but they just kind of bother me now and then. [...] I get scared seeing all these buttons and stuff, don’t really use them normally.”

More importantly, older adults can’t evade this problem by simply stopping using the new, complex functions on smartphones. Many necessary functions, like medical insurance, have already been integrated into smartphones. Sometimes older adults might ask a youngster to do the job or learn and memorize the operation, but at the risk of making mistakes.

Some participants don’t know how to perform certain tasks like making payments, as they are turned online now, unlike a few years ago when people walked to branches to pay the bills. The poorly designed interface of smartphone apps prevents the elders from completing their tasks.

4.3 Recurring Theme 3: Lack of Trust Cues

The theme of lack of trust cues is also identified in the responses of many participants.

Participants 1, 5, 7, 9, 11, and 13 all reported this problem. Lack of trust cues means that older adults can't distinguish between real and false information on the smartphone, especially when they are browsing online. Online scams can involve phone calls and text messages intended to fake government or company officials, which induce the receiver to leak important information like credit card numbers or important passwords. This can lead to serious consequences including being cheated out of their money. Such incidents have happened frequently in China recently. One of the participants, participant 11, has also experienced this. The experience of being cheated by an online scam made her stop storing more than a hundred Yuan in her phone, thus giving up a lot of online purchasing. She told the researcher:

“I have been a victim of fraud. Many things online are fake now, you can't trust them. [I] Yes. I had my smartphone some years ago. Somebody cheated money out of me when I was starting to use smartphones. Tens of thousands of Yuan, I think. [I] Since then the young people here have been taking care of my money. I only keep dozens of Yuan on my phone, so I won't worry about it being stolen. Now I don't use that feature (smartphone payment) anymore. I have been cheated so much money.”

Regarding this theme, participants told the researcher that they worry about online scams and privacy leaks. Participant 5 said that smartphones collect too much user information, and explicitly stated the need for more trust cues. “any overreach into user privacy should at least be disclosed so users can choose to comply or not, it should never be forced, [...] there should be

clear, visible reminders for the user about privacy risks,” said participant 5. When asked why to worry about scams, participant 7 replied that scam information is usually disguised as official text messages or phone calls. Take text messages for example: currently, official messages can only be distinguished by their heading and source phone number, so these are the trust cues of the message. However, most headings can be faked easily, and older adults don’t often check the number of who’s sending them, leading to misinterpretation that an official message has been sent. If extra trust cues are developed, such as automatic source phone number authentication and clear visual trust cues indicating whether the incoming message is from a trusted source, the problem can be greatly alleviated.

5. Limitations

This study isn’t a perfectly accurate identification of difficulties and barriers to smartphone use for older adults due to its potential limitations. The first limitation is the sampling strategy. Convenience sampling was adopted for this study because the secrecy of the resident database made random sampling impossible. However, convenience sampling introduces convenience error to the results (Simkus, 2022), which implies that there might be a heavier presence of sampling bias and selection bias, potentially skewing the results. Secondly, some older adults have barriers to communicating with the researcher. A majority of older adults in the nursing home have hearing impairments and cognitive, and thus might not understand the questions fully to give the best response. Many older adults tend to focus on only one main perceived difficulty in their conversation with the researcher, so interviews end quickly. All these signal the probability of response bias. Finally, the methodology choice of semi-structured interviews and thematic

analysis is qualitative. While qualitative studies do provide valuable insights, there is a lack of actual statistical data to back up the results of this study (e.g. What percentage of older adults suffer from intrusive advertising? Are there any difficulties that are more statistically significant than the identified ones?). The results are therefore an exploration of the inquiry, but only a rather primitive one, needing further research to validate and solidify the results.

6. Discussions

The original hypothesis states that complex features targeting young users and unnecessary functions are the main difficulties. Though the complexity theme partly resembles the “complex features” and “unnecessary features” proposed in the hypothesis, most parts of the results are substantially different from the original hypothesis. The results reveal that intrusive advertising, complex features and interactions, and lack of trust cues are some of the main interface-related difficulties of older adults. These factors make the smartphone use experience unpleasant and untrustworthy for older adults in Chengdu, hindering them from further usage.

7. Implications / Directions for Future Studies

This study examines the difficulties in the interface of smartphones and older adults that hinder the smartphone usage of elders. It can contribute to the existing academic community on this subject. The results of this study can serve as guiding design principles for user-friendly devices for older adults in China. The current prevalent elderly-friendly design principles include adopting text and object standards, intuitive control elements, and adding extra confirmations to reduce error; additionally, input control and natural language are also frequently mentioned in

designing user interfaces (Dodd et al., 2017). These design principles mostly address the complexity theme discovered in this study. Results from this study recommend that advertising problems and lack of trust cues also should be addressed in designing interfaces for older users. More explicit trust cues for official information, for example, can be included as an age-inclusive measure. Also, most older adults are not the targeting group of online advertisements, which means that companies can take action to show those older users fewer commercials and improve the smartphone experience of older adults.

The potential of informing policy and practice also stands out as an anticipated implication of this study. Up to now, there has long existed a divorce between policymaking and actual difficulties regarding smartphone usage by older people in many parts of China. Policymakers can refer to this study as an information source for developing better region-specific policies and practices. Studies in the same field also state that aiding future policy development is one of the important implications. In a comprehensive study by Vimalkumar and Jang (2020) of the multi-level digital divide of smartphone adoption across different nations, for example, the researchers recommended different policies be made for different nations.

Based on the results of this study, there are several recommendations for local policymakers or smartphone companies for better policies or practices:

- 1) Address the older people's demand for an ad-free online experience, or at least give them a more straightforward way to manage ad settings. Making such modifications ensures a smooth and trustworthy smartphone experience, and potentially restores a sense of autonomy for the elders.

2) Give the older adult the option to use simplified interface options or customize their smartphone according to the complexity levels they can handle and the advanced functions they wish to use.

3) The lack of trust cues expressed by older adults speaks to the need for a more trustworthy and comprehensible digital environment. To take an example, the “国家反诈中心” (Guo Jia Fan Zha Zhong Xin, National Anti-scam Center) app recently released by the Chinese government signals a step towards this vision. In the future, the government must take action to spread the use of such anti-scam apps and that smartphone companies work with the government to re-develop trust cues in smartphones.

Further research following this study can focus on extending the method from interviews to broader or deeper methods. Firstly, longitudinal studies can be conducted to observe changes in smartphone usage problems over time and gain insights into the more persisting problems. This kind of study can address the “lack of gerontological smart device-based research despite a growing interest in smartphone and tablet use for health management from older adults,” as mentioned by Wilson and Byrne in 2022. Secondly, studies with larger sample sizes and better sampling methods can be conducted to address the limitations of this study and get a more accurate and representative result. Thirdly, interventional studies can be conducted in supplement to this observational study. Experiments in interventional studies can be useful in quantitatively proving causation between difficulties and user reluctance.

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Appendix

a. Baseline Interview Question List

1. 您平常使用智能手机吗？ Do you often use smartphones?
2. 您主要用智能手机做什么？ What do you often do on smartphones?
3. 总体来说，您使用手机的体验方便易用吗？ Overall, are your experiences with smartphones pleasant and convenient?
4. 您认为您使用智能手机的困难和挑战有哪些？ What do you think are some difficulties you face when using smartphones?
5. 您可以仔细描述一下您遇到的这些挑战和困难吗？ Can you describe those challenges and difficulties you encounter in detail?
6. 您一般怎样解决遇到的困惑？ How do you normally solve challenges you meet?
7. 您是否认为手机的适老化还需要很大的改善？ Do you think smartphones still need a lot of improvements for older people?
8. 您是否认为您和您身边的人需要一些使用手机的培训或辅助？ Do you think you and your peers need training or assistance in using smartphones?

b. Sampling Locations

1. Tianchen Road (天辰路). Wuhou District, Chengdu. [TR]
2. Xincheng Property Management (馨城物业). No.58 Zhida Road Two, Wuhou District, Chengdu. [XP]
3. Lianghe Village (两河村). Xindu District, Chengdu. [LV]
4. Jinxin Jiujulefu Nursing home (锦欣九九乐福养老中心). No.1, 9, Xiyuan Road, Hezuo Street, Pidu District, Chengdu. [JJ]

Sampling Location	Participant Number 1-13
TR	1, 2
XP	3, 5, 7
LV	6, 10, 12, 13
JJ	4, 8, 9, 11

Table 2. Participants' Locations

c. Interview Transcripts, Participants 1-13.

Note: These interviews are transcribed automatically by Xun Fei Typewriting and then edited by the researcher to get rid of the meaningless repetitions, filler words, and/or errors caused by inaudible noises. Many interviews are conducted in the Chengdu dialect, so the responses might not fully conform to the conventions of modern Mandarin. After each Chinese transcript, an English translation is also provided for reference. This section is long, so to save reading effort, segments of transcripts mentioned in the paper are highlighted. Here's a sample highlighted text:

Sample highlighted text

Participant 1, Male

你平常要用智能手机吗?

我要用,我用了几年了。

你一般用智能手机干什么呢?

我们现在一般不干什么,。有很多功能我们不会去用,因为现在年龄大了,都是老人,那些新功能肯定就不怎么用。平常一般就打电话,还有上微信跟人家聊天,另外就是看看视频,还有这个小说,就这个。

我可以用你的手机看一下你的软件吗?

可以可以你看嘛。

你用手机的体验方不方便?

我觉得这个手机还可以,因为我们一般就用它来打打电话,还有发短信,现在我天天都跟我们家里年轻人发短信,平常看视频和看小说都很方便。

你觉得现在用手机有没有什么困难?有没有什么不方便的地方?

我觉得还好。一般都不会遇到什么不方便的地方。但是我用视频软件的时候,我用这个抖音的时候,我平常就会觉得里面可能有一些广告,里面可能就有诈骗。有些骗子你晓得不嘛?现在很多人都在网上,都要骗你的钱。只要你手机上有钱,他就有给你骗起跑了。现在我们都是让年轻人帮我们管手机上的钱,我们自己手机上就只有十几块钱都是年轻人在帮我们买东西,还有付钱,我们自己手机上没得啥子钱,你晓得不嘛,这样就不得遭骗。

确实,现在新闻上都有很多,就是很多被骗的案例。那你平常充话费交水费什么的时候要用手机交钱不呢?

不不，我都不得用手机交钱，都是年轻人帮忙弄的，我们一天就住在养老院里头，不用拿手机去交钱，就只是看看视频。

哦哦，好的。那手机上有没有什么功能你不会用呢？

你要说什么功能不会用，我觉得也没什么，因为我们这个年龄段的人用这个手机，其实平常会打电话看看微信消息就可以了，像看视频看小说这些平常都没有什么问题，我们也不会拿手机去干什么别的事情，不像有些年轻人，他可能会用很多功能，还要打什么视频通话，我们一般都不管那些。

所以你除了打电话看微信和一些娱乐软件之外，不会用手机干别的事情对吗？

对的，我用手机就用一些那些基本的功能。我们这个年龄很多其他人也都用了一些很基本的功能，不会去用很多现在出的高端功能，那些都是年轻人在用的。

你一般怎么解决你遇到的困难呢？

我们这边养老院里面有很多年轻人，我们一般就去找他们帮我们解决，像很多时候要联网，或者是点进了什么广告，我就叫他们来帮我修一下，年轻人会玩手机，一下就修好了，像很多复杂的功能我们平常都不管。也不怎么会用到。

你是否认为你和你身边的人需要一些在用手机方面的培训？

我觉得不用，我们平常用手机就很简单，就用那几个功能。可能年轻人需要学用手机，他们要用各种功能，我们一般聊聊天看看视频就好了。

哦，OK，好的。那就差不多了，谢谢你哈。

Do you use a smartphone?

Yes, I do. I been using it for several years.

What do you generally use your smartphone for?

Nowadays, we don't do much with it. It has many features that we don't use because we are old now, we are older people, so we can't use all those new features like youngsters. Normally, we just make phone calls and use WeChat to chat with people. Besides that, we watch videos and read novels, just that.

Can I take a look at the apps on your phone?

Sure, you can.

Do you find using the phone convenient?

I think this phone is okay because we mainly use it for making calls and sending texts. Nowadays, I text our family's youngsters every day. Watching videos and reading novels are also feels very convenient, they're all in those apps you know.

Do you find any difficulties with using your phone? Is there anything inconvenient?

I think it's generally fine, I don't usually encounter any inconveniences. However, when I use video apps like Douyin (TikTok), there really are a lot of advertisements in there, and I feel that there might be some scams inside. You know, there are scammers, right? Many people online just want to steal your money. As long as there's money on your phone, they'll try to swindle you. Now, we let the younger people manage our mobile money, we ourselves only keep around ten yuan or so on our phones, we let youngsters to help us shop and pay bills, we don't keep much money on our phones to avoid being scammed.

I understand that. Scams are a problem now, you can see it on the news. Do you use your phone to pay when you pay your phone bill, water bill, things like that?

No, I don't use my phone to make payments; the youngsters handle that for us. We just live in the nursing home and don't need to use the phone for payments, just for watching videos.

Oh, okay. Are there any features on the phone you have problems using?

If you ask what features I don't know how to use, I don't think there are any I can specify for you, because people of our age group, we mainly use the phone to make calls and check WeChat messages. Watching videos and reading novels are usually no problem. We don't use our phones for other things, unlike some young people who might use many features, including video calls. So we just don't even use these things, we wouldn't have problems using it. We generally don't bother with those.

So, other than making calls, checking WeChat, and some entertainment apps, you don't use your phone for other purposes, right?

That's right, I just use some of those basic functions. Many other people our age also use just the basic functions and don't bother with many of the advanced features that are mostly used by younger people.

How do you usually solve the problems you encounter?

Here in the nursing home, there are many young people, and we usually ask them for help. Like when we need to connect to the internet, or if I accidentally click on an ad, I call them to fix it. Young people know how to handle phones, and they fix it quickly. We don't really deal with many complex functions and don't often need them.

Do you think you and the people around you need some training on how to use smartphones?

I think it's not necessary. We use our phones very simply, with just a few functions. Maybe young people need to learn how to use phones for their purposes, I don't know what, but for us, chatting and watching videos are enough.

Oh, OK, that's about it then. Thank you!

Participant 2, Female

请问你平常要用智能手机吗?

我平常要用啊, 我们这些人平常都要用智能手机。

你平常要用手机上的哪些软件呢?

那我们这些人你说用手机其实也只是接个电话, 像你说的其他的那些软件啊什么的, 我们都不怎么用。

平常就按照自己的需求用就可以了是吗?

对的, 我们就接个电话打个电话这种事情。我们现在都有养老保险, 也没什么要在手机上去交的费用什么的, 所以平常也不会用那些其他的软件什么的, 现在网上骗子很多, 我也不想去用那些骗子软件。只能说方便还是方便, 但是到底方便多少我们也不知道, 因为有很多在上面的新功能, 我们也学不到, 平常不会怎么在这个上面去学。我们现在脑袋的反应力没有那么快。像平常支付钱那些, 我们都没有在上面支付。

那平常用手机的时候有没有什么特定的困难?

有的时候声音小, 我们自己调节不来就喊家里的娃儿调的。像亮度还有这个字的大小, 你想我们年龄大了肯定就要亮一点点嘛, 还有这个字也要调大一点点, 平常有什么问题就找这些家里的年轻人去帮我们调一下, 他们都会调。像这个手机里的内存本身不是很大, 所以说很多时候我们就要去删一些没有用的东西这样。很多时候自己操作不好, 就拿回家给娃儿操作。

你是有觉得因为手机上的功能太复杂, 所以不好操作吗?

是的, 就是上面很多地方太复杂了, 像有很多那些新功能, 我们自己的反应跟不上, 所以很多复杂的东西都不会用, 我们平常也没有花时间在这个上面去学。可能就是那些年轻人, 因为他们现在在管这个东西, 他们把很多东西都变复杂了, 他们自己肯定会用, 但是有的时候我在上面就不会操作, 你知道吗? 现在我的记忆不好, 有的时候进入这些页面的时候, 我也不记得我在干什么。上面有很多这种按键, 有很多东西我其实根本不需要。

所以就比较影响我。一般我遇到这种情况，都直接让家里的年轻人去帮忙搞一下。

很多时候都是年轻人帮忙是吗？自己是不是很难去搞懂手机里面的操作？

对的，手机里面的操作现在很复杂，但是有的时候有必须要用，现在大家都在用手机，所以我们就让家里的年轻人帮忙弄一下。

那像你这种情况，你觉得需不需要什么培训和帮助呢？

嗯，但是因为我们年纪大了，我们平常反应没那么快，可能就不会用那些新功能，平常也不怎么去点开看，所以就用打电话的功能就好了。那些最新的功能，我看到到处都是按键，我看着就有点害怕，平常也不怎么去用。

好的。

Do you normally use a smartphone?

Yes, I do use it regularly, we all use smartphones around here.

What apps do you usually use on your phone?

Actually, for us, it's mostly just for making phone calls. Like you mentioned, other apps and such, we hardly use them.

So, you just use it according to your needs?

Exactly, we just make and receive calls. We now have social security, and there's no need to pay anything on the phone, so we don't use other apps much. There are a lot of online scams, and I don't want to use those scammy apps. It's convenient, sure, but how convenient it truly is, we don't really know because there are many new features we can't learn, and we usually don't spend time learning them. Our reaction times aren't as quick anymore. Like paying money, we don't do that on the phone. Do you face any specific difficulties when using your phone?

Sometimes the volume is too low, and we can't adjust it ourselves, so we ask the kids at home to adjust it. Things like brightness and font size need to be increased because of our age, and any issues are usually handled by the younger people at home who know how to adjust these settings. The phone's memory isn't very large, so we often have to delete things we don't use. If we can't operate it well, we just take it home for the kids to handle.

Do you feel that the phone's features are too complex to operate?

Yes, it's just that there are many complex features that we can't keep up with, so we don't use them. We also haven't spent time learning these. **Maybe it's the young people, they are in charge now, and so they made everything more complex. I bet they don't have a problem using it, but I sometimes**

lose track of the operations on the phone. You know, I have a bad memory now, I can't remember what I want to do when I enter some pages. There were buttons everywhere, I don't think I even need those functions, but they just kind of bother me now and then. Usually, in these situations, I just let the young people at home help me out.

So, it's often the young people who help you with the phone?

Yes, the operations on the phone are very complex now, but sometimes it's necessary to use it since everyone is using smartphones, so we let the young people at home help us.

In your case, do you think you need any training or assistance?

Well, but since we are older, we don't react as quickly, and we probably won't use those new features. We hardly ever explore them, so we just stick to using it for making calls. Those latest features, I get scared seeing all these buttons and stuff, don't really use them normally.

Alright.

Participant 3, Male

你好，请问你平常要用智能手机吗？

哦，我要用我要用。

那你用手机用了多久了呢？

我用手机用了起码也有三四年了吧，从疫情的时候我就开始用手机了，当时疫情刚刚开始的时候，他们要各种健康码什么的，家里的年轻人就给我买了这个手机，我现在觉得用这个手机还挺方便的。

那你主要用智能手机做什么？

我平常用这个手机做的事情也不是很多，你看我手机上可以这个看小说，然后还可以跟他们发微信，现在这些人就经常喜欢给我发微信，你看吧，然后平常站岗的时候我就在这个里面看小说，还有看视频晓得不嘛，手机上面看视频方便，没事的时候就摸出来耍一下。还有就是我的医保社保卡都在这个上面看，你看他这个小程序这个微信小程序里面点进去就可以看我的医保，还有社保这些信息。以往都要去专门的地方办，现在在手机上就都看到了，你看到没有？还是很方便的。

哦，那平常你用手机还是用的挺多的。

对，我用的多，我用的多。现在基本上每天都要用。包括楼下他们那几个大娘都要用手机，以前都不用这个智能手机，我们以前用的都是按键，手机那个按键手机不能上网，你知道

吧，我们儿子前两年给我配的这个智能手机，你看这个就好用了，我天天在上面看这些东西，还要拍照对还要拍照，我平常用这个东西经常去各种地方拍照片，你看嘛，拍了之后还可以用微信发给别人，还有拍视频拍照片这些功能我都经常用，这个智能手机就是比原来的按键手机好用。

哦哦，好的，那除了比按键手机好用之外，你觉得你用这个手机有没有什么困难呢？

我觉得倒也没有什么困难。看我们平常用这些小程序，还要看小说发微信，我们天天都能正常用，哈哈。

那你有没有觉得哪些地方用着比较麻烦，你要专门去调，或者是有什么用起来不好的地方？

我就是觉得这个屏幕有的时候晚上看着太暗了，有点费眼睛，我有的时候晚上起来看这个手机啊，他就这个屏幕特别暗，没有什么光线，看小说那些就容易看不清楚，他那个亮度它会自动调，你知道吧？晚上的时候他自己就变暗了，平常都可以正常用。而且现在我用这个手机，他越来越费电，以前不用怎么充电，现在天天都要充电，可能用个三四个小时就没电了，晓得吧。没电了，他用着就很卡，有的时候看微信，看小说这些时候都很卡，所以平常要经常充电，而且有的时候这个屏幕不太灵，其他的感受都还是很方便，我们年龄大了，用这个智能手机，平常还是有很多帮助。

你一般怎么解决你遇到的这些困难呢？

一般我就找他们帮忙看一下嘛，我们宿舍里其他人他们有的会用手机，我就交给他们整一下就好了，要不就是给年轻人看一下，年轻人都会用。

好的，那你觉得手机这些上面还需要什么很大的改善吗？

就是他这个电池现在很不行，你知道吧，然后有的时候屏幕也不行，还有用着总是发烫，我觉得可以在这些方面做好一点，总体还是比较方便的。

那请问你觉不觉得你平常需要一些培训或者帮助才能用手机呢？

那肯定没有，那肯定不至于，就是有的时候卡没电了，这种情况平常我们都自己解决了，不需要什么培训。

嗯，好的好的，差不多就这些了，谢谢你哈。

Hello, may I ask if you usually use a smartphone?

Yes, I use it a lot.

How long have you used a smartphone?

I've been using a smartphone for at least three or four years now, starting from the time when the

pandemic began. Back then, various health codes were required, and the young people in my family bought me this phone. I find it quite convenient to use now.

What do you mainly use your smartphone for?

I don't do much with my phone; you see, I can read novels on it, and also send messages on WeChat. Nowadays, people frequently like to send me messages on WeChat. Look, and when I'm on duty, I read novels or watch videos on it. It's convenient to watch videos on the phone. When I'm free, I just take it out to play around. Also, my medical insurance and social security card details can be checked on this phone. Look, you just go into this WeChat mini-program and it shows my medical insurance and social security info. Before, we had to go to specific places to handle these, but now I can see everything on my phone. See? It's very convenient.

Oh, so you use your phone quite a lot.

Yes, I use it a lot, I really do. Nowadays, I use it practically every day. Even the older ladies downstairs use smartphones now. Before, we all used feature phones, those button phones that couldn't access the internet, you know. A couple of years ago, our son got me this smartphone, and it's really useful. I look up things on it every day, and also use it for taking photos. I often go to various places to take photos, and send them to others using WeChat. I frequently use those features like video recording and taking photos. This smartphone is just more useful than the old button phones.

Oh, okay. They are more useful than button phones. Do you find any difficulties in using this smartphone?

I don't really find it difficult. We use these mini-programs daily, read novels, send messages on WeChat. We can use it normally every day, haha.

I mean, do you find any aspect of using it cumbersome or problematic? Anything.

Well one issue is that the screen sometimes gets too dim at night, it makes my eyes tired. Sometimes I wake up at night to use my phone, and the screen is just so dim, lacking brightness, making it hard to read novels. It automatically adjusts its brightness, you know? It dims by itself at night, but otherwise, it's fine during the day. Also, the phone starts to drain battery faster now. It didn't need charging so often before, but now it needs to be charged daily, maybe every three or four hours. When the battery is low, it starts to lag, like when I'm reading WeChat messages or novels, so I need to charge it often. Sometimes the touchscreen isn't very responsive either, but other than that, it's still quite convenient overall. As we get older, having a smartphone really helps a lot.

How do you usually solve these problems you encounter?

Usually, I just ask others around me for help, like the people in our dorm who know how to use smartphones; they fix it for me, or I ask the young people, they all know how to use it.

Okay, do you think there are any improvements that are needed for smartphones?

Well, the battery life is not good, you know, and sometimes the screen isn't great either. It often gets hot when used. I think improvements could be made in these areas, but I think, it's still quite convenient.

Do you need some training or help to use your phone?

Definitely not, that's definitely not necessary. It's just sometimes it lags or runs out of battery, but we usually solve these issues on our own, no training needed.

Okay, we're done here, thank you!

Participant 4, Male

你平常要使用智能手机吗?

我要用, 我用的就是这个华为的。

那请问你平常要用手机做什么呢?

我就只用那个微信, 还有我要打电话。

哦哦, 好吧, 那像你平常用微信的时候, 会不会有什么功能不会操作呢?

嗯, 可能有一些功能不会用的, 或者是不想点进去的。

具体有哪些东西呢? 比如说那个视频通话你会不会用呢?

视频通话不会视频通话我会我今天上午才给我儿子打了个电话, 你看吧, 我给你看一下, 嗯。嗯就是这个看视频通话完它会显示已经通话了, 我现在点这个就可以跟他视频通话。

哦哦, 那像微信里面这些支付功能, 还有买票啊, 健康码呀, 这些在个人账号里的功能可以用吗?

你说什么功能?

就是付款, 还有收款, 然后各种买票, 查看线路信息等等的。

这个用的比较少, 主要是担心广告。我们这边有人在手机上面看了广告之后买车票, 结果就亏钱了。我手机里面也有钱, 听他们说那些广告点进去都是骗你钱的, 所以我不怎么用, 平常就是去买东西的时候用一下支付功能。

哦，我明白了，那你觉得这些功能需要很大的改善，才能让你们更好的去使用吗？

我觉得可能也不是需要什么改善，因为我们年龄大了之后也不会用这些功能，平常不怎么会想去用，所以可能改善了以后作用也不大，我就是这么想的。

我明白了，谢谢你的参与。

Do you normally use a smartphone?

Yes, I use this Huawei one.

What do you usually use your phone for?

I only use WeChat and make phone calls.

Oh, okay. When you use WeChat, are there any features that you don't know how to use or don't want to explore?

Yes, there might be some features that I don't know how to use or just don't want to click on.

Can you specify which features? For example, do you know how to use video calls?

I do know how to use video calls. I just made a video call to my son this morning. Look, I'll show you. See, after the video call, it shows that the call was made. I can click here to start a video call with him.

Oh, what about other features in WeChat like payment functions, buying tickets, health codes and such in your personal account?

What features are you referring to?

Like this, you can make payments, receive payments, buy tickets, check route information, and so on.

I seldom use them, mainly because of the ads. I heard somebody living here bought ticket or something after seeing an ad on his phone and loses money. I also have money in my phone, I heard those ads are all made to scam your money, so I don't really use them. I just use the payment feature when buying stuff offline.

Oh, I understand. Do you think these features need significant improvements to make them easier for you to use?

I don't think they necessarily need improvements. Because as we get older, we don't use these

features much anyway. I don't really want to use them, so even if they are improved, it might not make much of a difference to me. That's how I see it.

I understand. Thank you for participating.

Participant 5, Male

您平常智能手机的哪些软件用得更多呢？

电话，微信，还有一些支付方面的软件，还有看新闻啊，还有一些资料啊，嗯，大概就这些。

你平常工作的时候会用手机吗？

会，它是一个基本工具。联系客服，联系同事，储存资料，转换资料，这些都会用到它。

你觉得总体来说使用手机是否比较方便。

肯定咯，有了手机这个平台手机它就相当于小型电脑，原来的电话就只有一个简单的通话加短消息功能，但现在这个电脑的很多功能都在手机上都能够体现了，简直不能太方便，方便多了。

那用手机的过程中有没有任何的困难或者挑战呢？

目前还没有遇到任何方面的任何方面的。

它任何问题，比如说屏幕上的问题或者是字体或者用起来上面有地方不清楚的，平常可能有些困扰的这些或者涉及不人性化的地方有没有？

那就是有些个别的 app 的那个操作比较繁琐一点，步骤多了一点，可能是为了安全性的考虑吧，它的步骤或是设置要多一些。还有一个，在输入上，我想他可能应该有那个语音输入吧，但是我经常比较常用的就是手写，相对麻烦一些，输入这个可能跟个人的习惯有关系吧，总体还是感觉比较好。也就说现在一些基本功能基本能满足我的工作和生活。也有比较复杂点儿的 app 呢，但是我们也不怎么用。另外，现在手机的信息收集很多时候超出了一定的范围，比如说手机信息，比如说敏感词啊，甚至于包括图像的这种违规采集。是否有这种违规情况我们不太清楚，但是从这个 app 上精准推送的广告来看，这种现象是存在的。老年人很多时候不能完全控制这些东西，我觉得这种对使用者的这种隐私的越界行为至少你应该提出来告知对方，对方可以愿意配合你可以不愿意配合你，你不能强行。还有一个就是很多 app 的使用，甚至一些最基本的功能，包括一些政府应该承担的这个事项，或者商家应该这个承担的法定事项里面加进了很多商业化的一些行为，比如这个开发票的这个 app，在这个过程中，他就会强行的需要你开发票的用户提供比如头像啊，位置信息啊等等。这些信息会被对方采集到。但是事实上开发票这个事情应该商家应该承担，而且是应该商家无条件的承担，而且应该给用户提供最直白的方面，对吧，而不是让我们这

种用户在使用的时候操作很多个步骤，而且还要贡献出个人的很多信息给对方，而且是第3方，才能获得服务。当然这些实际上是应该说是手机的软件设置嘛，那关于硬件设置呢，就是现在的手机在使用上物理按键明显的少了，更多的都是在界面上去操作，对我们来说，就是不太爱接受新鲜事物的年纪比较大的人呢，可能也会有这种心理障碍，但不是说实实在在这种操作障碍。我的经验就是突破了心理障碍也就能接受新鲜的东西，基本上能够能够把新的东西通过学习嘛，然后再加上大量的运用，嗯，都还是能接受的。

你觉得总体来说，手机能怎样去做一些提升？

有些时候要在明显的位置去给用户一个提醒，你比如很多恶意的 app，他会在在安全方面，就是说在在你使用者不小心点到了某些设置的时候，就会出现信息泄露。我说的这个信息泄露是指的，比如说这个你的支付的系统，或者说你的银行卡系统，或者说你任何涉及到金钱支付方面的嘛，都很容易出现这种被被骗，被诈骗的不法分子控制，那么很多时候，我们都是刻意的打开设置通用里面的一些东西去进行一个一个安全方面的设置，希望在这方面得到一个规避，但是这种往往很多时候就要经常在网上查找这种教程，才得以有一个安全的保障。就说这方面的话，我觉得在初始设置上啊，都应该有一个明确的提示，你比如对方要可以浏览你的通讯录啊，对方可以浏览你的这个相册啊。这些设置功能其实就应该应该有明确的提醒，而且应该要限制这些 app 采集人们的个人信息。

好的好的，谢谢你。还有什么要补充的吗？

我感觉都说的差不多了。很多这些问题其实都可以避免的，希望后面这些方面做出一些改变吧。

What apps do you use a lot on your smartphone?

I use the phone, WeChat, some payment-related apps, news apps, and some other informational apps.

Do you use your smartphone during work?

Yes, it's an essential tool. I use it to contact customer service, colleagues, store data, transfer data.

Do you think it is convenient to use a smartphone?

Definitely. Smartphone can be acting like mini-computer these days. The old phones only had call and text functions, but now many computer functions are also available on smartphones. Don't tell me about how convenient they are, really better now.

Have you encountered any difficulties or challenges while using your smartphone?

I haven't encountered any specific problems.

Anything counts here. Issues with the screen? unclear fonts, or user interface problems maybe?

So far, there haven't been any major issues. But some individual apps might be a bit difficult to operate because they involve so many steps to set up, possibly for security reasons. Also, I often use handwriting input, which is a bit more cumbersome than voice input that I think is available. Overall, though, I feel quite satisfied as the basic features meet my work and personal needs. There are more complex apps, but we don't use them much. Additionally, the collection of information by smartphones sometimes exceeds necessary limits, such as sensitive words or unauthorized image collection, they do that for checking violations, like if you said anything harmful or so. It's not clear if there really are violations, but the targeted ads I receive suggest it happens. It feels like users, especially older ones, can't fully control this, and **any overreach into user privacy should at least be disclosed so users can choose to comply or not, it should never be forced**. Moreover, many apps, even those for basic services which the government or businesses should handle, incorporate too many commercial activities, like apps for invoicing that force users to provide personal information like photos and location. This data collection should be the responsibility of the business or government, and they should manage it straightforwardly without making users go through many steps or give up personal information to third parties just to use their the service.

How do you think smartphones could be improved?

Sometimes, **there should be clear, visible reminders for the user about privacy risks**, like when you unintentionally click on settings changes, that can lead to data breaches. This concern is really a thing because there is the risk of getting scamed and having your money transferred away. Often, we need to deliberately adjust settings or seek online tutorials for secure use. Initial settings should include clear hints about what data apps can access, like contacts or photo albums something. There really should be explicit notifications and restrictions on apps collecting personal information.

Thank you. Is there anything else you would like to add?

I think that covers most of it. Many of these issues are avoidable, and I hope there will be some changes in these areas in the future.

Participant 6, Female

请问你平常用手机都要用哪些功能呢?

我平常就接电话嘛，哈哈，还要看微信。其他功能太多了，不怎么用。

除了打电话和微信之外，你还要用手机的其他功能吗?

要看下抖音，刷下抖音。

用抖音的时候会遇到什么不便吗?

不喜欢看抖音广告，看到了我都要去关掉。

嗯，有没有其他使用起来不太方便的地方呢？

我觉得就上网那些不太方便，我们平常都不上网。

现在大家喜欢用手机上的各种功能，像什么支付功能，还有平常看新闻什么的。你平常不用这些功能吗？

这些功能都没用过，我只有平常用的那些功能。我们老年人压根都不需要那些。就只有打微信啊，刷一下小视频呀什么的。

你之前说过有抖音广告的问题，你平常经常看到这些广告吗？有没有想过怎么解决？

经常看到这些广告，平常经常看到。遇到这种广告的话，我们就去把它关了，哈哈，也没有什么其他的办法。平常广告最多的地方就是我们看节目的时候，我喜欢看《金牌调解》。

《金牌调解》？

对对，江苏卫视的节目。调解那些有冲突的人嘛，哈哈。就是抖音上的片段，精彩片段，我平常看的时候会有很多广告。遇到就会把它关掉就好了。他们跟我说广告有很多都是骗钱的，但是也有的时候我看不出来是广告，现在有的广告都跟视频差不多，有的时候他们都说我非要去看广告，其实我有的时候就是看不出来，哈哈。

如果有机会的话，你觉得你会愿意学用手机的各种其他功能吗？

啊，脑筋不够用。脑筋不够用。手机的功能我们平常都不敢用多了。

嗯，好好，那就这样，谢谢你。

What functions do you normally use on your mobile phone?

I just make calls, haha, and check WeChat. There are too many other functions; I don't really use them.

Besides making calls and using WeChat, do you use any other functions on your phone?

Yeah I watch Douyin, scroll through Douyin videos.

Have you encountered any inconveniences when using Douyin?

I don't like the ads on Douyin, I always close them when I see them.

Ok. Is there anything else that is inconvenient to use?

It is not convenient to go online, we don't usually use the internet.

Nowadays, everyone likes to use various functions on their phones, like payment functions, reading news, etc. Don't you use these functions?

I've never used those functions; I only use the ones I'm accustomed to. We elderly people really don't need all that. Just WeChat, watching some short videos, stuff like that.

You mentioned earlier about the problem with Douyin ads, do you often see these ads? Have you thought about how to deal with them?

I see those ads frequently, all the time. When I encounter them, I just close them, hahaha, there's no other way. The ads are most frequent when we watch shows. I like watching "Gold Medal Mediator (金牌调解)," haha.

"Gold Medal Mediator (金牌调解)"?

Yea, a Jiangsu TV program. Mediating people with conflicts, you know, haha, I like watching it. It's the exciting clips on Douyin that I watch, and there are lots of ads when I do. I just close them when they come up. They told me not to click on the ads because they cheat money out of you. Sometimes I can't tell if those ads are part of the video, and they sometimes blame me for watching ads all the time, because they don't know why I like ads that much. Actually, I just can't tell, haha.

If you had the chance, do you think you would be willing to learn to use all the other functions on your phone?

Ah, My brain can't handle it. My brain can't handle it. We are afraid to use too many functions on the phone.

Hmm, okay, that'll be all, thank you.

Participant 7, Male

请问你平常要不要用这个智能手机呢?

我平常要用，平常肯定要用，工作的时候又没事，可能就会摸出来用一会儿，我用这个手机已经用了有两三年了。

你主要用这个手机干什么呢?

用手机干什么呀？主要就是打电话接电话，还有跟他们发微信平常工作的时候没事就点开看看视频，就在现在手机上面的那个抖音你知道吧。

总体来说，你觉得手机好不好用呢？

这个手机用起来还是好用，我们比如说我们就打电话接电话，还有平常看个抖音，像什么下载什么的都是他们帮我们做，哦对，都是他们帮我们做的。平常我们用手机都是没事情摸出来耍一耍，也不用什么高级的功能，有些东西我们自己不会操作的，我们都尽量不会去用。

现在你们觉得用手机有没有什么困难？

我觉得现在用手机还是有一些困难，一个就是我才说的，就是有一些高级功能，像什么抖音里面的购物的功能，还有发视频还要跟他们做直播，我听到他们有些人在做直播，这些功能我都不会用，还有就是像那个微信里的视频通话，打视频电话我也不回答，但是平常接电话打电话，这些功能我都在用，还是比较方便，但是现在的功能太多了。另外就是经常有乱七八糟的短信，还有广告，这些东西都很烦人。很多时候很影响我用这个手机，你像我们老年人平常都不是看看短信，还要看看抖音上面的视频，但是短信里面就经常有人给你发不同的消息，什么卖这个卖那个的消息乱七八糟的，肯定很多都是骗子，还有抖音上的购物，我们老年人不怎么会购物，他经常给我推购物的卖东西的人我平常都不看知道吧，但是也不知道怎么关。感觉用起来很麻烦。

一般遇到这种时候都让年轻人去解决吗？

对对，我们单位里有很多年轻人，他们会用手机，他们帮我下载东西啊，还有上次他们看我手机里有什么其他的软件好像是诈骗的，他们就给我删了。我一般都找他们去下载东西，还有打开微信里别人发的东西什么的。像图片什么的。我们搞不懂。

你觉得需不需要一些培训或者是辅助来帮助你们用手机呢？

这个呀，我觉得平常我们年纪大了也不会用什么高级的功能，所以培训什么的可能也不太需要，平常我们就打打电话，还有聊微信，哈哈。我觉得手机可以改进一下把上面那些乱七八糟的信息删一下平常我。看短信的时候就不会看到那么多广告，还有那么多卖东西的人。主要是这个。另外一个就是，应该帮助我们这些人去看假消息。有很多诈骗的都是伪装成政府号码给你发短信，你点了他就知道你的账号密码。就把你的钱转走了。如果有这方面的帮助就很好。

好的，谢谢你哈。还有什么要补充吗？

嗯，现在肯定年轻人用手机用的比我们好吧，可能他们可以学用那些功能，我们不太会耍那个。你晓得嘛，我们都只用这些基本的功能。其他的没什么要说的，我也不是很懂这个手机上的东西。

Do you often use smartphones?

Yes, I usually need to use it, especially at work when there's nothing much going on, I might take it out and use it for a while. I have been using this phone for about two or three years now.

What do you mainly use this smartphone for?

What do I use the phone for? Mainly for making and receiving calls, and sending WeChat messages. When I'm free at work, I usually open it to watch videos, like on Douyin, you know?

Overall, do you think the smartphone is easy to use?

This phone is easy to use, like, we just make and receive calls and watch some Douyin videos. Things like downloading apps are done by others for us. Yes, they help us with that. We usually just play with the phone when we're free, not using a lot of features. There are some things we don't know how to operate, and we generally avoid using them.

Do you find any difficulties using smartphones now?

I think there are some difficulties with using smartphones now. For one, there are some advanced features I mentioned, like the shopping features in Douyin, or uploading videos and doing live streams. I've heard some people do live streams, but I don't know how to use these features. Also, I don't really use video calls on Wechat or whatever. But making regular calls, those features I still use, and they are quite convenient. However, the phone now has too many functions. Another issue is frequent spam messages and advertisements, which are very annoying. They often affect my use of the phone. Like us elderly, we usually just check messages or watch videos on Douyin, but the messages often contain various spam about selling this and that, most of which are scams. There's also shopping on Douyin, which we elderly don't usually do. They often do these sales ads, which I usually ignore, but I don't know how to turn them off. It feels very troublesome.

Do you normally ask younger people to help with these issues?

Yes, yes. There are many young people in our office who know how to use smartphones. They help me download stuff, and once they even found some scam apps on my phone and deleted them. I usually ask them to download things for me, and to open things others send on WeChat. Images or so. We don't understand those

Do you think you need some training or assistance to help you use smartphones?

Well, I think as we are older, we don't use many advanced features, so maybe we don't really need training. We just make calls and chat on WeChat, haha. I think it would be better if the phone could filter out all that spam. If it could delete those annoying messages, I wouldn't see so many ads and sales pitches when I check messages. That's mainly it. Another assistance I really want is that I think somebody should tell us how to tell the fake messages. Many scammers disguise as government officials now, once you click on the link, they get your credit card number and password, they just take your money. I will be good to have some help there.

Okay, thank you. Is there anything else you want to mention?

Well, the young people can clearly use smartphones better than we do. Maybe they can learn how to do fancy things on the phone, you know, we would just stick to basic things. Not really much to say, I'm not an expert of these smartphones.

Participant 8, Female

请问你平常用智能手机吗？

我用手机用的比较少。我们这边养老院里面用手机的人都不多，因为平常也不需要干什么，他们他们 b 栋的那几个老人喜欢看视频，还有他们跟我说在手机上看小说，还有什么银行卡在手机上面，那个我都不会整。

哦，那你一天大概用多久呢？

说不准，我觉得我用的比较少，每天可能就晚上的时候拿出来用一下。还有他们给我打电话的时候，我拿来接电话，主要就是这个。

平常觉得用手机的时候方便不？

我这个我觉得我没有发言权，因为我平常用手机用的很少，我一天就用那么一会儿，我觉得就我用的体验来说还是很方便，嗯，但是因为我不用那些高级的功能，所以就跟按键手机也没有很大的区别。最大的可能就是他现在上面没有那些按钮，都是在屏幕上操作的，这个大屏幕看图片很方便很清晰。

你觉得高级的功能有哪些不会用的，为什么平常不用这些功能呢？

我平常在养老院生活，那些支付功能我们都不太需要。基本上都是在里面的小卖部买东西，我们都用现金买东西，他们小卖部的人也都收现金，所以他们很多人说的手机支付我们都不用的，而且这样也避免被诈骗。很多人还说手机上可以刷视频，刷小说，我基本上都不去看，我平常就跟院子里的其他人闲摆闲聊一下。之前隔壁有人给我安那个什么视频软件，还有看新闻的软件，我隔两天就让人帮我删了。那些软件，现在反应跟不上，里面东西太多了，像那个新闻软件里面点进去就跳出来各种各样的东西，感觉看新闻上不太方便，有太多的按键。字太小了，像蚂蚁一样大，我们现在不戴眼镜都看不清楚，我平常又不想天天戴眼镜看手机，所以也就不经常用。

好的，这个我明白了，您用手机还有什么其他困难或者疑惑的地方吗？

每天要用的操作自己都已经会了，其他的软件我不需要的，我就让他们删了，所以现在我每天打电话这些都没问题

那你觉得手机可以多改善一下，让您这样的人也能用各种新功能吗？

我觉得他如果改善一下，把那些功能都做的简单一些，然后把他的字体放大一点，屏幕做亮一点，适合老年人用的话，可能会很好。把它弄得太复杂了，跳出来各种各样的广告，还有乱七八糟的信息的话，我们用起来就很不舒服，用起来不舒服就会把它删了。所以就是这个方面。

你觉得需要这方面的培训，让你更好的用是这些新功能吗？

不用那些培训，反正我们现在记忆力不好，脑子跟不上所以这种新功能平常也都不会怎么去用了。

哦，明白了。谢谢你。

Do you regularly use a smartphone?

I don't use my phone very much. Not many people use smartphones here in the nursing home because we don't really need to. Some of the elderly folks in building B like to watch videos and they've told me about reading novels on their phones and managing their bank cards on them, but I don't know how to do all that.

How long do you use your phone each day?

It's hard to say; I think I use it quite sparingly. Maybe just in the evenings for a little while. Also, when people call me, I use it to answer the calls. That's mainly it.

Do you find it convenient to use your smartphone?

I don't think I really have much to say on that, as I rarely use my phone. I only use it for a little while each day, and from what I experience, it seems convenient enough. But since I don't use the advanced features, it's not much different from using a basic phone. The biggest difference might be that it doesn't have physical buttons; everything is done on the screen, which makes viewing photos very clear and convenient.

What advanced features do you find difficult to use, and why don't you usually use these features?

Living in the nursing home, we don't really need features like mobile payments. We usually buy things from the small store inside, and we all pay with cash. The store accepts cash, so we don't use mobile payments, which also helps prevent scams. Many people talk about watching videos or reading novels on their phones, but I generally don't do that. I just chat with other people in the yard. Someone once installed a video app and a news app for me, but I had them deleted after a couple of days. These apps are too much to keep up with; for example, the news app is cluttered and inconvenient with too many things popping up, and the text is too small, like ants. We can't see it clearly without glasses, and I don't want to wear glasses all the time to use my phone, so I hardly use it.

Is there anything else about using your smartphone that you find difficult or confusing?

I know all the operations I need for daily use, and I had the other apps deleted, so making calls and such is no problem for me.

Do you think smartphones could be improved to make it easier for people like you to use the new features?

If they simplified the features a bit, made the text larger, and the screen brighter, it would probably be better for older people. When they make it too complicated with too many ads and cluttered information, it becomes uncomfortable to use, and we just end up deleting those features. So, that's the main issue.

Do you think training to help you better use these new features would be necessary?

We don't need that training; our memory isn't what it used to be, and we can't keep up, so we wouldn't really use those new features much anyway.

Okay. Thank you.

Participant 9, Female

请问你平常要用智能手机吗?

我要用手机啊。现在大家都要用手机吧。

是的是的。那你用手机一般是做什么呢?

哦,我每天都看新闻。

看新闻是吗?是视频还是新闻软件?

有很多软件都可以看新闻,我可以打开给你看一眼,你看这个腾讯新闻,网易新闻,央广网央视新闻这些我们平常都要看,除了打电话之外,我每天都要看很多的新闻。有些新闻软件里面也可以看视频。比较关心国际上发生的一些事情,所以就经常去检查新闻软件。

这些软件你用起来方便吗?

挺方便的,平时点进去就可以在里面翻到新闻,我现在每天都要在里面读好多条新闻。主要是新闻软件里的东西比以往的报纸多很多,而且报纸拿着不方便,现在用手机很小巧玲珑,拿着就可以看新闻,感觉比以往轻便了很多。

看新闻的过程中有发现任何的问题或者不方便的地方吗?

现在这些新闻软件比较商业化，我觉得可能就导致用起来没有那么顺畅。很多人在里面打广告。腾讯新闻里面的广告最多，点进去之后首页上就有很多的广告比较影响我去读新闻的内容。视频里的广告最多了，视频里的广告有各种各样的什么洗发水，还有餐厅的广告，平常我都不看的，我都直接跳过。点到广告里面了，这样它就自动买东西，你知道吧，因为现在都很商业化的，要么给你买东西，要么给你充钱到什么会员里面。反正就想尽办法要忽悠你的钱。

明白了，你觉得这些软件要改进的话，主要就是去除里面的广告吗？

对，还有就是要做的更安全一些，现在新闻里天天都有说被诈骗了几十万几百万的，如果有办法保护我们这些老年人的钱包就更好了，哈哈。

诈骗确实是一个问题，很多老年人都在说。而且电视上也经常播报诈骗问题。

就是呀，所以现在我们都比较担心这个诈骗的问题。

你需不需要要一些培训或者帮助来让你们免受诈骗的威胁？

培训可能没有太大的必要，我觉得主要的还是把那些软件做得更安全一些，然后少做一些广告。

明白。就到这里了，谢谢您的参与。

Do you usually need to use a smartphone?

Yes, I need to use a phone. Nowadays, everyone needs one.

Right, right. What do you usually use your phone for?

Oh, I check the news every day.

You watch the news? Is it through videos or news apps?

There are many apps where you can read the news. Let me show you; look here at Tencent News, NetEase News, CCTV News—all of these I use regularly. Besides making calls, I read a lot of news every day. Some of these news apps also have videos. I'm particularly interested in international events, so I frequently check these news apps.

Are these apps easy to use?

They're quite convenient. Usually, I just click into them and can scroll through to find news. I read many articles daily. The main thing is that these news apps have more content than traditional newspapers, and they're more convenient than carrying newspapers around. Using a smartphone is

very handy and makes reading news much lighter than before.

Have you encountered any problems or inconveniences while reading the news?

Nowadays, these news apps are quite commercialized, which I think makes them a bit less smooth to use. There are a lot of ads. Tencent News, for example, has the most ads; when you open it, the homepage is full of ads which distracts from reading the news. Ads are most prevalent in videos—they include all sorts of ads, like shampoo or restaurant ads, which I usually skip over. If you accidentally click on an ad, it might automatically make a purchase. You know, because it's all very commercialized now—either they try to sell you something or get you to subscribe to some membership. Basically, they're always finding ways to take your money.

I see. So, you think these apps should primarily focus on removing ads?

Yes, and they should also be made safer. Every day in the news, you hear about people being scammed out of hundreds of thousands, so if there was a way to protect our wallets, especially for us older folks, that would be great, haha.

Scams are indeed an issue, something many older people talk about. And it's often reported on TV too.

Exactly, so we're quite worried about these scams.

Do you think you need some training or help to protect yourselves from scams?

Training might not be very necessary. I think the main thing is to make these apps safer and reduce the number of ads.

Understood. That's all for now, thank you for participating.

Participant 10, Female

请问你平常用智能手机吗?

啊,我经常用智能手机。

你一般用智能手机干什么呢?

一般是就是交流啊,然后看新闻看视频以及跟家人朋友之间的联系,包括支付功能。总的来说,你觉得手机方便好好用吗?

挺方便的,嗯,就是对眼睛不太友好。

是屏幕方面的问题吗?

我是觉得手机很方便的同时,然后它有很多东西会让你嗯要经常的使用,导致你眼睛呢跟这个手机屏幕这种光感屏幕经常的这个刺激眼睛,所以就导致眼睛会干涩啊,甚至视力下降。

好的好的,你一般怎么解决遇到的问题呢?

嗯,我会有意识的控制使用手机的时间,然后还有就是看手机的时候,嗯就是不要长时间的盯着屏幕,那么有的时候可以听手机上面的一些语音的东西,而不是纯粹的看手机上面的字体,这样的话就会好一些,一个是控制这个总的使用时间二个是控制每一次使用的时长。

你觉得在解决这些问题方面,手机还需要很大的改善吗?

需要。我觉得手机在给我们带来方便的同时也占用了或耗用了我们太多的时间让我们在很多没有意义的东西上面,花了太多的时间。比如说小视频其实对我们的生活没有太大的影响,纯粹就是一个娱乐,也许就是放松一下,但是有时候一放松就会花太多时间在上面,嗯,最后导致你看了之后觉得一无所获毫无意义,但是实际上你的时间成本进去了,你的眼睛也受到了伤害。

好的好的。

Do you usually use a smartphone?

Yes, I often use a smartphone.

What do you normally use your smartphone for?

Mostly for communication, then for watching news and videos, and for keeping in touch with family and friends, including using its payment features. Overall, do you find smartphones convenient and easy to use?

They are quite convenient, but they are not very friendly to the eyes.

Is it an issue with the screen?

I think while smartphones are convenient, they also have a lot of content that makes you want to use them often, leading to frequent exposure to the screen's light, which can irritate the eyes, causing dryness and even a decline in vision.

Alright, how do you normally solve the problems you encounter?

Well, I consciously control the time I spend on my phone, and when I do use it, I try not to stare at

the screen for long periods. Sometimes, I listen to audio content on the phone instead of just reading text, which helps. So, one is controlling the total usage time and the other is controlling the duration of each use.

Do you think there is still a lot of room for improvement in smartphones in solving these problems?

Yes. I think smartphones, while convenient, also consume or occupy too much of our time on many meaningless things. For instance, short videos really don't impact our lives much; they are just for entertainment, perhaps for relaxation, but sometimes relaxing can take up too much time, leading to a feeling of emptiness afterwards, even your time and your eyesight can be compromised.

Alright, thank you.

Participant 11, Female

请问你平常要用智能手机吗？用了有多久了？

我要用手机，我要用手机，可能用了有三四年了吧。

你平时用智能手机干什么呢？

我平常就是没事的时候拿出来玩一下，像刷抖音打打游戏，还有想用微信上的那些东西嘛，就是没事的时候玩。有的时候还要在抖音上发视频。

哦，还要在抖音上发视频吗？

对的对的，有的时候要在抖音上发视频，平常还要看抖音，我们可能还玩玩游戏。

您智能手机上的软件都方便好用吗？

哦，我手机上的有些软件我怕诈骗，我儿子都给我删掉了，你知道吧，有很多软件，儿子都把我删了，现在我一般就刷抖音，有的时候在抖音上发视频，有事情的话就打电话给他，晓得不。以前我的这个手机上也有好多软件，他全部给我删了，主要就是现在网上诈骗的太多了。唉，我以前就遭过，现在网上很多东西都是假的，根本不能相信。

真的吗，你以前遭过诈骗吗？

对，我几年之前用手机的时候，刚刚开始用手机的时候就被诈骗过，当时被骗了好几十万。现在就是年轻人在帮我付钱，我的手机上只留了十几块钱，这样就不担心被骗了。所以现在一般都不用这个了，当时我被骗了好多哟。

哦哦哦，所以现在都比较在意网上的骗子？

对，就是现在很害怕网上的骗子，现在就是害怕被骗。

是不是养老院里大家用手机的都比较害怕被诈骗？

嗯嗯，对，就是就是就是这样的，自从我的工资都遭骗了以后，我的儿子就把软件都删了，那些骗子软件都删了，把我的钱全部都取了，就是害怕再被骗。

哦哦，所以你觉得用手机主要的问题就是怕网上的诈骗吗？

对的对的，肯定是的，我们这边养老院里的老人都很害怕网上这种诈骗的东西你晓得不？现在天天都有这种诈骗，有很多骗子软件，还有很多骗子发信息，主要是被骗了，他就把你的钱全部转走了。转钱这些方面我们简直搞不懂，都是我儿子帮我做的。

好的好的，我明白了，那你觉得你和你身边的人需不需要一些用手机的培训呢？

感觉可以，主要就是这个诈骗的问题太严重了，如果可以解决这个问题，也可以，也不错。对。像我们对其他这些新功能都不追求了，平常就上个抖音看视频还要发视频这些，但是就怕骗子，有很多骗子在网上你知道吧。

我明白了，差不多就这些。你有什么要补充的吗？

没有没有。

好的，谢谢你的配合哈！

Do you use a smartphone? How long have you used it?

I do use a phone, I probably been using it for about three or four years now.

What do you usually do with your smartphone?

Normally, I just play it when I have nothing else to do, like browsing Douyin, playing games, and using WeChat, just to pass the time. Sometimes I also post videos on Douyin.

Oh, you post videos on Douyin?

Yes, I do post some videos on Douyin and also watch others'; we might also play games.

Are the apps on your smartphone convenient and easy to use?

Well, I'm scared of scams within some apps on my phone, so my son has deleted them for me. You know, there were a lot of apps on my phone but my son deleted them. Now I mostly browse Douyin, sometimes post videos, and if I need anything, I call him, you know? I used to have many apps on my phone, and he deleted all of them, mainly because there are too many scams online nowadays.

I have been a victim of fraud. Many things online are fake now, you can't trust them.

Really? You have been scammed before?

Yes. I had my smartphone some years ago. Somebody cheated money out of me when I was starting to use smartphones. Tens of thousands of Yuan, I think. Since then the young people here have been taking care of my money. I only keep dozens of Yuan on my phone, so I won't worry about it being stolen. Now I don't use that feature anymore. I have been cheated of so much money.

Oh, so now you are particularly concerned about online scammers?

Yes, I am now very afraid of online scammers.

Is it common in the nursing home for everyone to be afraid of being scammed on their phones?

Yes, yes, that's right. Ever since I was scammed out of my salary, my son has deleted those scam apps and withdrew all my money; we are afraid of being scammed again.

Oh, so you think the main issue with using a smartphone is the fear of online scams?

Definitely, the elderly here in our nursing home are all very afraid of these online scams, there are scams every day, lots of scam apps, and many scammers sending messages. They transfer your money away. We really don't understand these money transfer processes; it's my son who handles them for me.

Alright, I understand. Do you think some trainings might help you at this point?

It might be good; the problem with scams is really serious. If this issue could be resolved, that would also be good. Yes. We don't really pursue other new features at this point; we just use Douyin to watch and post videos, but we are scared of scammers because, well, there are many of them online, you know.

I understand, that's about it. Do you have anything to add?

No, nothing.

Alright, thank you for your cooperation.

Interviewee 12, Male

你用的是这个智能手机吗?

对的。

你平常用手机主要干什么呢?

啊，我平常就看看视频，还有发发短信，看看微信什么的。我看的事情也不多，因为我每天有其他的事情，没什么时间来看手机，一般就是中午的时候拿起手机来玩一下，你知道吧。

除了平常正常使用之外，有没有觉得用起来很困难的地方呢？

每个东西都有他自己的问题吧，像在这个智能手机上面，我每天都看到广告。我就特别讨厌广告。

你觉得广告是一个很严重的问题吗？

我觉得现在线上的广告越来越多了，现在很多地方都有那种各式各样的广告，基本上哪儿都是，你看这个信息软件，这个信息软件就是发手机号那个，就是用手机号收发信息的那个软件，他们每天都给我发垃圾消息，都是广告，你看这个这一条说的是有个什么交手机费的折扣这种都是假的，都不能信，家里的年轻人跟我们说的很多我要用的软件也天天给我发很多我根本不想看的东西。这个学习软件里面就有很多广告，我根本就不看，因为我是一个党员，很多的党员都用这个信息软件给我发消息，而不是微信，因为他们不会用微信，每天我看这个的时候，我都要点到这些烦人的广告里面去，我也不知道怎么取消，还有就是我看那个视频的时候，广告经常跳出来，你根本取消不了，很多时候都关不掉。你知道吧，所以我最烦这个东西。

哦，我明白了。你觉得手机在这方面还需要很多改善吗？

我们这些人也都不看广告，这些广告留在里面完全就是打扰我们使用。我看一条视频就弹出来一个广告，看一条视频就弹出了一个广告，到最后根本不想看视频了，太烦人了这些东西。

哦哦，好的。其他方面还有什么问题需要辅助吗？

不是，其他方面的我都会用，但是就是这些广告还有很多给我推送的东西不明所以的我平常根本就不看，我觉得这个很烦人。好多软件里面的那些按键我根本就不会点，平常都不会看他们。主要就是这些问题。

我明白了，谢谢你哈。

嗯，嗯，不客气。

Do you use this smartphone?

Yes.

What do you mainly use your phone for?

Well, I usually watch videos, send texts, and check WeChat and such. I don't spend much time on my phone because I have other things to do every day. I usually just pick it up and play with it at noon.

Besides normal usage, do you find any difficulties using it?

Every item has its own issues, like on this smartphone, I see ads every day. I hate advertisements.

Do you think ads are a serious problem?

(Ads are) So annoying. I feel like there are more ads online than ever before. There are so many places that ads can slip into, they are basically everywhere. Look at this message app, Phone number message type of app, not Wechat. they send me spam messages every day, all of them are ads. And this one says there's another discount for paying my phone bill online now. All fake, you can't believe these. Some apps I use also send me things I don't even want to read. Like in this study app. You know, I'm a party member, and some older members use this messaging app instead of Wechat (A chatting app, similar to WhatsApp), because, you know, they can't handle Wechat. Every day when I read the messages I had to click in these meaningless ads, I don't know how to cancel them. And when I was watching videos, those ads also pop out. You can do nothing about it. No, you can't close them sometimes.

Oh, I see. Do you think a lot of improvements are needed in this area for smartphones?

We older people don't watch ads, these ads are just a nuisance during our use. I watch a video and an ad pops up, another video, another ad, and in the end, I just don't want to watch videos anymore, it's too annoying.

Oh, okay. Are there other problems that can be solved by maybe a little assistance service?

No, I can use other aspects, but it's just these ads and many pushed things that I don't understand, I really don't look at them, I find it very annoying. There are many buttons in many apps that I just don't know how to press, I usually don't look at them. These are the main issues.

I understand, thank you.

Mm, mm, you're welcome.

Participant 13, Male

你一直在用智能手机吗?

是的, 我用了好几年了。

你平常用智能手机一般做什么呢？

我就是打电话看微信，还有就是看那个小说。

看小说吗？一般是在哪里看小说呢？

我就是用那个看小说的软件，就这个番茄免费小说，我平常没事的时候就把它点开看，现在已经看了很多本了。这个软件平常一直是免费的，所以我就不用怎么在上面花钱。

你觉得用手机方便吗？

还是很方便的，我觉得。我现在打电话用微信之类的都没问题，而且平常无聊的时候也可以看小说。有的时候就用这个手机去支付，用微信里面那个功能扫一下就可以付钱，感觉很节省时间。

有没有什么困难？

我觉得平常用电话和微信这些软件都没有什么困难的地方，因为这些都是很基本的软件，平常在这里面也没有什么不会用的功能。倒是那个免费小说软件，平常会有很多广告，感觉就像他们必须要给你看一个视频，一个广告，每翻几页都要给你看，这个软件看起来是免费的，但是如果你去点广告的话，你肯定就要被骗钱了。

哦，好的，所以主要还是担心被骗钱吗？

担心被骗钱，因为现在好多钱都是存在手机里的，如果被骗了的话也是很大一笔钱。以往都是随身带在身上的，就不会有这种担心，现在到处都是诈骗，所以要格外小心。

我理解。除了这点之外，有什么其他的问题吗？

我觉得就是他那个小说软件里。功能有点太多了。那里面一直在加功能，现在还有什么看视频的功能，还可以加好友，我们平时都用不到，我们就看个小说，这些功能还是删除了比较好。有的时候功能越多反而太复杂了，越影响我们的操作。

Do you use a smartphone?

For several years now.

What are something you usually do with your smartphone?

I make calls, browse WeChat, and read novels on smartphone.

Read novels? How do you usually read them?

I use an app specifically for reading novels, called "Tomato Free Novels." I usually just open it up

and read whenever I'm free. I've read quite a few books by now. The app is always free, so I don't really have to spend money on it.

Do you find it generally convenient to use your smartphone?

It's very convenient, I think. I have no problems making calls or using WeChat, and I can read novels when I'm bored. Sometimes, I use my phone to make payments too; just scanning with the WeChat payment feature saves a lot of time.

Do you face any difficulties?

I don't really find it difficult to use basic apps like the phone and WeChat because these are very straightforward. However, the free novel app often has a lot of ads. **It's like they have to show you a video, an ad, every few pages. That app seems completely free, but you are definitely going to lose money if you click on the ads.**

Oh, I see. So, your main concern is about being tricked into losing money?

Yes, I'm worried about losing money because nowadays, a lot of money is stored on our phones. If you get tricked, it could be a significant loss. In the past, when you carried cash, this wasn't a concern. But now, with scams everywhere, you have to be extra careful.

I understand. Besides this, do you have any other issues?

I think it's mainly with that novel app. It has too many features. They keep adding new functions, like watching videos or adding friends, which we don't really need. We just want to read novels. It would be better to remove those extra features. Sometimes, having too many features just makes things too complicated and affects our use.
